

Studies on Some Less-familiar Metal Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part XIX. Colloidal Properties of Cobalt Ferrocyanide

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Different aspects of the colloidal properties of cobalt ferrocyanide have been studied. The results on the variation in viscosity with the period of dialysis provide evidence for the hydrolytic properties of cobalt ferrocyanide. Coagulation experiments with uni-, bi- and trivalent ions fit well in Bhattacharya's equation on slow coagulation only with the concentrated sol. The phenomenon of acclimatisation and ionic antagonism is also well exhibited by this sol.

In an earlier communication¹ the hydrolytic and adsorptive properties of cobalt ferrocyanide were reported. Estimation of the free ferrocyanide in the dialysed and undialysed samples at various dilutions and at different temperatures provided evidence of hydrolysis of the freshly precipitated complex.

In view of the interesting results obtained on the basis of these studies, it was thought worthwhile to carry out comprehensive investigations on the colloidal properties of the complex. The work described here deals with variations in viscosity of cobalt ferrocyanide sol with dialysis, slow coagulation of the sol by addition of electrolytes, and a study of the phenomenon of ionic antagonism and acclimatisation with this sol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium ferrocyanide solution was estimated by titrating against a standard KMnO_4 solution². The requisite amount of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in conductivity water and cobalt was estimated³ as cobalt ammonium phosphate. Electrolytes used were of A. R. quality and the solutions were made in conductivity water.

Cobalt Ferrocyanide Sol.—The sol was prepared by the method of double decomposition. The amounts of cobalt chloride and ferrocyanide required to precipitate 2.5 g. of cobalt ferrocyanide were calculated from their stoichiometric relationship.

Calculated amounts of the reactants were mixed in the ratio of 1 equivalent of CoCl_2 : 5/4 equivalents of K_4FeCy_6 . The sol could only be obtained when cobalt chloride solution was gradually added to diluted potassium ferrocyanide solution with constant stirring. Dialysis was carried out by keeping distilled water in the outer vessel.

1. Malik and Bhattacharya, *Agra Univ. J. Res. (Science)*, 1957, 6, 25.
2. De Eacon, *Ann. Chim. Pharm.*, 1854, 90, 160.
3. Cumming and Kay, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1945, p. 306.

Viscosity Experiments.—Scarpa's method⁴, modified by Farrow⁵ and improved by Prasad *et al.*⁶, was employed. The formula used takes into account times t_1 and t_2 required for filling and emptying the bulb of the viscometer under a definite pressure; v is the volume of the bulb, R , the radius of the capillary, and l , its length :

$$\eta = \frac{\pi PR^4}{8LV} \times \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} = \text{const.} \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

If the same temperature and pressure were employed, the value of the constant for a particular viscometer could be determined by measuring t_1 and t_2 for a liquid of known viscosity. One litre of the sol was prepared and 100 ml of the sol was kept in six different dialysing bags for dialysis. The bags were suspended in distilled water which was changed at fixed intervals and fresh distilled water was poured in the dialysing trough. The total volume of the sol was made to 200 ml in each case for the dialysed sol and the viscosities were determined. In other words, the concentrations of the sols were kept constant in every case and errors due to diffusion and osmosis were avoided as far as possible. Measurements were made at 20°, 25°, 30°, 35°, and 40°.

Time of Slow Coagulation.—An aliquot of 5 ml of the sol was taken in steam-dried Pyrex test tubes and varying amounts of electrolytes (M -NaCl, 0.005*M*-BaCl₂, 0.005*M*-AlCl₃) and the total volumes were made to 10 ml by addition of conductivity water. The concentrations of the various electrolytes in the sols were so adjusted that the minimum time of coagulation was near about 30 min. in each case. Sols of concentrations A, A/2, and A/4 were used and the time at which the sol particles left the surface of the sol was taken as the time of coagulation.

Acclimatisation.—Table I records the volume of each electrolyte required to coagulate 5 ml of the cobalt ferrocyanide sol in 1 hr. and also the volume of each electrolyte which shows the maximum acclimatisation effect when a small quantity of the electrolyte is in contact with 5 ml of the sol for 15 min.

TABLE I

Conc. of cobalt ferrocyanide sol = 1.25 g./litre. Total volume of the sol + electrolyte + water = 10 ml. Temp. = 31° ± 0.1°.

Electrolyte.	Volume of the electrolytes.	*Ppt. conc.	Volume of max. accl. effect.	*Max. accl.
A. Sol A.				
N-NaCl	0.65 ml	0.06500	0.05 ml	0.00500
N/2-KCl	1.35	0.06750	0.10	0.00500
N/5-HCl	0.65	0.01300	0.03	0.00060
N/100-BaCl ₂	0.75	0.00075	0.10	0.00010
N/50-CaCl ₂	0.50	0.00100	0.06	0.00012
B. Sol A/2.				
N-NaCl	0.50	0.05000	0.04	0.00400
N/2-KCl	1.35	0.06750	0.20	0.01000
N/5-HCl	0.40	0.00800	0.04	0.00080
N/100-BaCl ₂	0.75	0.00075	0.10	0.00010
N/50-CaCl ₂	0.45	0.00090	0.05	0.00010

*Units expressed in g. equiv./litre.

4. *Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347.

6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1384.

Ionic Antagonism.—Table II shows the phenomenon of ionic antagonism with mixed electrolytes in the case of cobalt ferrocyanide sol.

TABLE II

Time of coagulation = 1 hr. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Volume and ppt. conc. of primary electrolyte.	Secondary electrolyte.		Conc. of sec. electrolyte (in g./litre).
$N/2$ -KCl (1.35) 0.0675	N -NaCl (0.20)		0.020000
	$N/100$ -BaCl ₂ (0.15)		0.000150
	$N/200$ -Al ₂ Cl ₆ (0.15)		0.000075
$N/100$ -BaCl ₂ (0.75) 0.00075	$N/2$ -KCl (0.05)		0.002500
	$N/50$ -CaCl ₂ (0.04)		0.000080
	$N/200$ -Al ₂ Cl ₆ (0.03)		0.000015
$N/200$ -Al ₂ Cl ₆ (1.10) 0.00055	$N/2$ -KCl (0.02)		0.001000
	$N/100$ -BaCl ₂ (0.05)		0.000050

N. B. Figures in parentheses refer to volumes in ml.

DISCUSSION

The viscosity-time of dialysis curves do not exhibit any regular change in viscosity (Fig. 1). On the other hand, the viscosity first decreases during the first two days and then

FIG. 1 Cyanide sol (1: 5/4).
Curves I—V refer respectively to 20°, 25°, 30°, 35°, and 40°.

continuously increases after the third day, showing tendency of attaining constancy with prolonged dialysis. Such variations may be attributed to factors like gradual removal of stabilising ions and the hydrolysis of the complex on dialysis. Normally the removal of the stabilising ions would result in a decrease in charge and consequent increase in viscosity. Since a decrease in viscosity is observed in initial stages, it is quite likely that the second factor is very much operative here and the hydroxyl ions formed due to hydrolysis of the sol increase the charge on the sol particles. Two experimental observations, besides those reported in an earlier communication¹, lend support to the hydrolysis concept during the course of dialysis. Firstly, the freshly

precipitated complex on dilution and subsequent heating shows a marked increase in pH , indicating a change of the type:

Secondly, the walls of the dialysing bag turn red, thereby showing the occurrence of deposition of hydrous oxide of iron and cobalt also during dialysis.

The initial decrease in viscosity takes place due to adsorption of the hydroxyl ions on sol particles. When hydrolysis is stopped, removal of the stabilising ions continues to take place, resulting in an increase in viscosity. This is maintained till the magnitude of hydration, corresponding to the minimum charge required to keep the sol stable, is attained, after which hardly any change in viscosity is observed. The slight tendency of decrease in viscosity after six days of dialysis indicates sensitisation of the sol on prolonged dialysis.

Effect of Electrolytes.—The precipitation concentrations in mM/litre for the various electrolytes required for coagulating the sol in 1 hr. are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Cobalt ferrocyanide sol (g./litre).	NaCl.	KCl.	HCl.	BaCl ₂ .	Al ₂ Cl ₆ .
Sol A (1.25)	65.0	67.5	13.0	0.75	0.550
A/2 (0.6250)	50.0	65.5	8.0	0.75	0.375
A/4 (0.3125).	50.0	65.0	8.0	0.75	0.235

It appears from Table III that although the Schulze-Hardy rule is approximately followed, the order of coagulating power being $Al^{3+} > Ba^{2+} > H^+ > Na^+ > K^+$, the effect of dilution of the sol on the precipitation concentration values is not marked. In all cases, except with Al^{3+} , there is no difference between the precipitation concentration values of sols of concentration A/2 and A/4. Since there is very little difference in the amounts of electrolyte required for coagulating the sol in a specific period for the sols of different dilution, the sol appears to become highly stabilised on dilution.

Recently Bhattacharya and Kumar⁷ investigated the relationship between the electrolyte concentration, c , and reciprocal of the time of coagulation ' t ' in the region of slow coagulation and obtained hyperbolic curves in the majority of cases, although in a few isolated cases their plots were straight lines. In our case, plots of c against ' $1/t$ ' did not provide hyperbolic curves. Straight lines, however, could be realised in all cases with concentrated sol (A) and a few isolated cases (Fig. 2 and 3). Here too, the behaviour with dilute sols is abnormal.

Bhattacharya put forward an empirical equation:

$$c = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$$

where a , m , and n are constants on the basis of their experiments with copper ferrocyanide, ferric oxide, and As_2S_3 sols. They employed the plots of ' c ' and ' $1/t$ ' to obtain the value of

7. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 179, 638; 1952, 29, 687, 759,

$\hat{a}$ (critical stability concentration) and the plots (straight line) of ' $1/(c-a)$ ' and ' t ' to get the values of the constants m and n . In the present studies, the plots between ' $1/(c-a)$ ' and ' t ' also provided straight lines in all cases except with sol of concentration A/4. The values of a , m , and n are shown in Table IV.

FIG. 2

Curve 10 : Sol A— M - NaCl 11 : Sol A/2— M - NaCl 12 : Sol A/4— M - NaCl 13 : Sol A— $M/200$ - Al_2Cl_6 14 : Sol A/2— $M/200$ - Al_2Cl_6 Curve 15 : Sol A/4— $M/200$ - Al_2Cl_6 16 : Sol A— $M/200$ - BaCl_2 17 : Sol A/2— $M/200$ - BaCl_2 18 : Sol A/4— $M/200$ - BaCl_2

On examining the values of the constants of the equation, the values of ' a ', ' m ', and ' n ' are found generally to decrease with the valency of the cation of the electrolytes used. In cases where intercept is obtained from a straight line, the results are more reliable. It evidently shows that the Schulze-Hardy rule is followed for the different cations employed. Bhattacharya's equation is, however, not strictly followed in the case of highly dilute sol. It is quite possible since factors like the number of particles per unit volume and the

distance between the colloid particles play more prominent role than adsorption, hydration of ions, ionic velocities, etc. in the coagulation of dilute sols.

TABLE IV

Sol.	Electrolytes.	a (mM/litre).	m (mM/litre).	π (min ⁻¹).
A/1	M-NaCl	50.500	333.30	576.000
A/2	M-NaCl	42.000	333.30	576.000
A/4	M-NaCl	41.000	..	..
A/1	M/200-BaCl ₂	0.275	0.09	0.594
A/2	M/200-BaCl ₂	0.305	0.66	0.297
A/4	M/200-BaCl ₂	0.315	..	..
A/1	M/200-Al ₂ Cl ₆	0.510	0.33	0.045
A/2	M/200-Al ₂ Cl ₆	0.325	0.16	0.041
A/4	M/200-Al ₂ Cl ₆	0.220	..	..

The experiments on acclimatisation show that the stability of the cobalt ferrocyanide gradually increases with gradual addition of the electrolytes up to a certain concentra-

tion beyond which the stability of the sol begins to decrease (Table I). Hence there is an optimum concentration of the electrolyte to produce maximum stability and may be named as maximum acclimatisation concentration of the electrolyte.

FIG. 3

Ligends of the curves correspond to those in Fig. 2

may be adsorbed on the colloidal material, resulting in its enhanced stability.

The results on ionic antagonism (Table II) show that the total amount of mixed electrolytes required to coagulate the sol in 1 hr. is greater than the precipitation concentration of the primary electrolyte. Many workers have suggested that the adsorption of ions carrying the same charge as the colloid may very well explain these results. Attention may be drawn to another important factor, viz., the change in the ionic concentration of the ions, that takes place when electrolytes are mixed together and it is this effective ion-concentration of the mixed electrolytes which should be given due consideration while explaining the results on ionic antagonism.

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